

Brazil releases two new rice cultivars

E. P. Silveira, researcher, Federal Agricultural Research System (EMBRAPA), Rua Goncalves Bias, 570, 90000 Porto Alegre, Rio Grande do Sul State, Brazil

BR2 is the new name given to IRRI line IR442-2-58 (IR95-31-4/Leb Mue Nahng), and BR-IRGA-409 the new name for P790-B4-51 (IR930-2/IR665-31-1-4), a semidwarf line developed at Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT).

EMBRAPA introduced and released BR2 for upland conditions of Piauí State. BR2 matures in 120 days and has long, slender grains. In the field it has tolerance for or resistance to drought, blast, and lodging, and it yields from 2.6 to 4.2 t/ha.

BR-IRGA-409 was introduced, selected, and released through cooperative work among EEA-IRGA (the Rio Grande do Sul rice research station), a DNPEA-U.S. Agency for International Development Loan Agreement 512-L-007, and EMBRAPA. It has long slender grain, matures in 105 days, is tolerant of blast and Helminthosporium leaf spot, and has given consistent yields during the past 4 years (see table). BR-IRGA-409 gave stable yields of 6.7–6.9 t/ha at 40 and

Performance of BR-IRGA-409 at different locations and under different levels of nitrogen. Rio Grande do Sul State, Brazil, 1974–1978.

Variety	2- year mean yield (t/ha)						
	Preliminary yield trials		Regional yield trials				
	40 kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	
	<i>Pelotas</i>		<i>Cachoeira do Sul</i>				
BR-IRGA-409	6.7	6.9	6.1	6.4	6.3	6.1	
Bluebelle	5.9	6.3	3.2	3.9	3.7	3.9	
EEA 406	6.2	6.3	5.2	5.1	5.6	5.7	
CICA 4	5.4	7.8	5.7	5.9	6.4	6.4	
	<i>Cachoeirinha</i>		<i>Palmares (CRI)</i>				
BR-IRGA-409	6.9	6.7	5.8	6.3	6.1	6.8	
Bluebelle	4.1	4.3	3.6	3.9	4.4	5.2	
EEA 406	4.7	4.6	—	—	—	—	
CICA 4	4.7	5.3	4.6	4.8	5.0	5.1	
			<i>Pelotas</i>				
BR-IRGA-409			5.1	5.4	5.3	5.5	
Bluebelle			4.2	4.3	4.2	4.0	
EEA-406			5.3	4.7	5.0	4.4	
CICA 4			5.2	5.4	5.5	5.5	
			<i>Santa Vitória</i>				
BR-IRGA-409			4.7	4.5	4.6	5.1	
Bluebelle			3.1	3.3	3.9	3.8	
EEA 406			4.7	4.7	4.6	5.1	
CICA 4			3.3	4.0	4.5	4.2	
			<i>Uruguiana</i>				
BR-IRGA-409			7.8	7.9	8.5	7.3	
Bluebelle			5.5	5.4	5.4	5.1	
EEA 406			—	—	—	—	
CICA 4			—	—	—	—	

80 kg N/ha; at the same levels Bluebelle yielded 4.1–6.3 t/ha; EEA 406, 4.6–6.3 t/ha; and CICA 4, 4.7–7.0 t/ha. At

0, 30, 60, and 90 kg N/ha, it again performed well, with yields ranging from 5.1 to 8.5 t/ha. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Effect of different tungro-infected varieties as virus sources on the infectivity of *Nephotettix virescens*

A. Hasanuddin and K. C. Ling, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute

The infectivity of *Nephotettix virescens* after feeding on tungro-diseased plants of IR8, IR34, and TN1 was determined by the test-tube inoculation method. The diseased plants were inoculated 7 days after soaking, were kept in the greenhouse for 40 days, and then used as virus sources for 1,440 adult insects.

Infectivity of *Nephotettix virescens* fed on tungro-diseased rice plants of different varieties at acquisition access periods of 2, 24, and 96 hours. IRRI, 1979.

Rice variety (tungro source)	Insects (total no.)	2h	24 h	96 h
		<i>Infective insects (%)</i>		
IR8	480	37 a	33 a	40 a
IR34	480	26 a	13 a	35 a
TN1	480	83 b	88 b	90 b
		<i>Insect retention period (days)</i>		
IR8	323	1.3 a	1.4 a	1.5 a
IR34	364	1.2 a	1.3 a	1.6 a
TN1	356	1.7 b	1.9 b	2.2 b
		<i>Infected seedlings (%)</i>		
IR8	3,317	7 a	7 a	7 a
IR34	3,277	3 a	2 a	7 a
TN1	3,213	18 b	23 b	27 b